

The Effect of Effective Communication & Work Motivation on Nurse Performance in ICU Room at Panembahan Senopati Hospital, Bantul

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 01 April 2022	Background: Improving the quality of health services, especially in hospitals, can be achieved by implementing health services by the standards and ethics of professional services. The performance of nurses is one of the essential components that can describe the fulfillment of these service standards and ethics. Effective communication and work motivation are two factors that will affect the performance of nurses. Methods: This study is a quantitative study with a cross-sectional design involving 12 nurses in the ICU ward of Panembahan Senopati Hospital Bantul. Research data was obtained using a questionnaire. Results: There is no relationship between effective communication and nurse performance ($p = 0.166$). There was no relationship between work motivation and the performance of nurses in the ICU ward at Panembahan Senopati Hospital Bantul ($p = 0.488$). Conclusion: Effective communication and work motivation of nurses did not affect the performance of nurses in the ICU Room at Panembahan Senopati Hospital, Bantul.
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KEYWORDS: Effective Communication; Work Motivation; Nurse Performance	

I. PRELIMINARY

At this time, the Indonesian government is always trying to create a community condition where the Indonesian people are healthy both physically and mentally. The government is well aware that a healthy society will support the country's development efforts. The development will be challenging if unhealthy community conditions do not support it. Therefore, the Indonesian government is required to create a quality health service system so that it can be utilized by all levels of society without obstacles, both economically and non-economically. Officially the government has attempted, by issuing a letter by [1], stating that the goal of government towards the development of the health sector in Indonesia is the achievement of the community, nation, and state, where the population can access quality health services with justice and equity.

As for efforts to improve the quality of services delivered to the community, there has been a success in improving health facilities to look better. Especially for the procurement of health facilities such as hospitals and health centers in Indonesia. The progress that has shown the conditions as planned. By this reality, it must acknowledge that the government's efforts have been successful in increasing the number of hospitals in Indonesia [2]

However, we must realize that there are still several considered things to provide quality health services. One of the indicators that we can see in efforts to improve the quality of health services is how much utilization of the health facilities themselves. Based on population statistical data, the number of people who use hospital facilities in 2017 is 10.3%, which, when compared to the percentage of Indonesian people using public health facilities in the same year, is 27.1%. In addition, other categories use as an indicator of the low use of hospital services, namely BOR (Bed Occupancy Rate) or the average percentage of beds used every day. So far, the BOR achievement is still below the standard, with the BOR level achieved by public hospitals in Indonesia in the range of 50% [3], while the relevant standard value should get 70-80%. The results of comparing the standard value between the number of patients in hospitalized conditions with the total operating costs of the hospital as a whole.

In terms of improving the quality of health services, improving the quality of health services should be directed at providing quality health services, namely the implementation of health services following the standards and ethics of professional services. In this case, the hospital as a health service unit must increase the quality of its work

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by providing services to the community to be more leverage to provide the best referral place and provide satisfaction to patients, public health center, and practicing doctors [2]. It requires good nurse performance, especially for patients treated intensively, where errors must minimize significantly.

In this regard, three essential factors affect the quality of service providers, namely leadership, communication, and control systems. The leader influences [4] a worker's behavior. Leadership style influences how a worker thinks and behaves to influence the organization directly. The existence of a morale booster from the leader to his subordinates will increase the workability of his workers.

Apart from the leadership aspect, based on research by [5], communication in an organization has a vital function to convey information to all parts or individuals. In addition, communication is also in the delivery of suggestions to improve the organization's quality. With excellent and effective communication, a leader can improve the mistakes made by his subordinates without the subordinates feeling offended or blamed.

The last thing that can influence behavior in providing services is the control system. Behavioral control systems use to improve worker performance because, with control, we can anticipate things that have the potential to cause problems early on. Two control systems are widely known, namely control systems based on behavior and control systems based on results. The control system related to service behavior is based on the fact that the worker's behavior will depend on what kind of control he will get. If the control system is positive, it will impact the positive behavior of the worker and vice versa. This study aims to determine the relationship between effective communication and work motivation with the performance of nurses in the ICU Room at Panembahan Senopati Hospital Bantul.

II. METHOD

This study is a quantitative study using a cross-sectional design involving 12 nurses in the ICU ward of Panembahan Senopati Hospital, Bantul. The study was held in August-September 2019. Inclusion criteria: (1) Implementing nurses in the ICU ward of Panembahan Senopati Hospital Bantul and (2) Implementing nurses willing to be respondents. Exclusion criteria: (1) Nurses who refused, were on leave, were sick, and could not attend the study, and (2) Nurses who did not have direct contact with patients—research data obtained through filling out a questionnaire. The questionnaire instrument in this study was an adaptation questionnaire from previous research, namely the ABC study.

III. RESULT

Table 1. Relationship between Effective Communication and Nurse Performance in the ICU Room at Panembahan Senopati Hospital, Bantul

Effective communication	Nurse Performance				Total	p Score
	Poorly		Well			
	N	%	N	%		
Poorly	1	8,3	1	8,3	2	16,6
Well	1	8,3	9	75,1	10	83,4
Total	2	16,6	10	83,4	12	100,0

The table above shows that as many as 2 (16.6%) respondents had poor effective communication, with 1 (8.3%) respondents performing poorly and 1 (8.3%) respondents performing well. A total of 10 (83.4%) respondents have good effective communication, with 1 (8.3%) respondents whose performance is not good and 9 (75.1%) of respondents whose performance is good. Statistical test results obtained p-value = 0.166 ($p > 0.05$), meaning that H1 is rejected and Ho is accepted, it can be concluded that there is no relationship between effective communication and nurse performance.

Table 2. Scores of Effective Communication Components Based on Nurse Performance in the ICU Room at Panembahan Senopati Hospital, Bantul

Variable	Mean	p Value
SBAR Knowledge		
On Good Performance Nurses	3,4 ± 0,84	0,418 ⁱ
In Poor Performance Nurses	4,0 ± 1,41	
Application of Situation		
On Good Performance Nurses	11,0 ± 1,89	0,758 ^m
In Poor Performance Nurses	11,0 ± 1,41	
Application of Background		
On Good Performance Nurses	7,5 ± 1,08	0,606 ^m
In Poor Performance Nurses	7,0 ± 1,41	
Application of Assessment		
On Good Performance Nurses	16,7 ± 2,83	0,758 ^m
In Poor Performance	16,5 ± 2,12	
Application of Recommendation		
On Good Performance Nurses	39,0 ± 5,09	0,909 ^m
In Poor Performance	38,5 ± 4,94	

Based on the table above, we can see that nurses with good performance have a higher average score of background application, assessment application, and recommendation application. Meanwhile, nurses with poor performance have a higher mean score of SBAR knowledge. However, there is no difference in the mean score of SBAR knowledge,

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background, assessment, and recommendation application between nurses with good performance and nurses with poor performance (all have p-value > 0.05).

Table 3. The relationship between the motivation of nurses and the performance of nurses in the ICU Room at Panembahan Senopati Hospital Bantul (n=12)

Nurse's Motivation	Nurse's Performance				Total		p Value
	Not good		Good		N	%	
	N	%	N	%			
Not good	0	0	2	16,6	2	16,6	0,488
Good	2	16,6	8	66,7	10	83,4	
Total	2	16,6	10	83,4	12	100,0	

The table above shows that as many as 2 (16.6%) respondents had poor nurse motivation, with 2 (16.6%) respondents having good performance. As many as 10 (83.4%) respondents have good nurse motivation, with 2 (16.6%) respondents having poor performance and 8 (83.4%) respondents had a good performance. Statistical test results obtained p-value = 0.488 (p > 0.05), meaning that H1 is rejected and Ho is accepted, it can be concluded that the motivation of nurses is not related to the performance of nurses.

Table 4. Scores of Nurse Motivation Components Based on Nurse Performance in the ICU Room at Panembahan Senopati Hospital, Bantul

Variable	Mean	p Value
Recognition/Awards		
On Good Performance Nurses	7,8 ± 1,31	0,454 ⁱ
In Poor Performance Nurses	7,0 ± 1,41	
Achievement		
On Good Performance Nurses	7,5 ± 1,5	-
In Poor Performance Nurses	-	
Responsibility		
On Good Performance Nurses	15,9 ± 1,1	0,77 ⁱ
In Poor Performance Nurses	18,0 ± 2,82	
Promotion/Raise		
On Good Performance Nurses	19,7 ± 1,7	0,34 ⁱ
In Poor Performance Nurses	21,0 ± 1,41	
Interpersonal Relations		
On Good Performance Nurses	8,6 ± 0,84	0,758 ^m
In Poor Performance Nurses	9,0 ± 1,41	
Wages		
On Good Performance Nurses	15,2 ± 2,14	-
In Poor Performance Nurses	-	
Supervision		
On Good Performance Nurses	19,6 ± 3,71	0,414 ⁱ
In Poor Performance Nurses	22,0 ± 2,82	

Variable	Mean	p Value
Working Condition		
On Good Performance Nurses	3,7 ± 0,82	0,273 ^m
In Poor Performance Nurses	4,5 ± 0,7	

Note : ⁱ = independent sample T test; ^m = Mann Whitney

Based on the table above, we can see that nurses with good performance have a higher average motivation score in recognition/award than nurses with poor performance. Meanwhile, nurses with poor performance have a higher average motivation score regarding responsibility, promotion, interpersonal relationships, supervision, and working conditions than nurses with good performance. However, there was no difference in the mean scores for the components of recognition/award, achievement, responsibility, promotion, interpersonal relations, salary, supervision, and working conditions (all had p > 0.05).

IV. DISCUSSION

This study will discuss the research results related to effective nurse communication, nurse work motivation, nurse performance, and the relationship between effective communication and work motivation on nurse performance.

Characteristics of Research Subjects

This study found that the age description of the subjects of this study was distributed evenly in three age groups, namely 21-30 years, 31-40 years, 41-50 years, each of which amounted to 4 people. The gender of the research subjects is also relatively balanced between men and women, although the number of men is slightly higher. Based on the level of education, most nurses have a D3 nursing education level. The majority of the working period of this research subject is 1-10 years. Based on the findings above, we can see that relative age and gender do not affect the findings in this study because they show a relatively homogeneous picture. Meanwhile, the education level and tenure findings may influence because there is a disparity in education level and tenure. Research subjects with a D3 education level and those with 1-10 years of service are more numerous.

Effective Communication

The results of the effective communication research of nurses in the ICU room at Panembahan Senopati Hospital Bantul based on table 4.5 are suitable. According to the researcher, effective communication is essential for nurses. The clarity and accuracy of information about all nursing interventions given to patients determine the quality of nursing care services themselves. This is in line with the theory [6]. Effective communication is the main element of patient safety goals, so ineffective communication clear and accurate aspects must be built according to the context of language and information, systematically and culture to

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reduce misunderstandings that result in errors in providing nursing care [7].

The communication strategy in this research is to use effective communication based on SBAR (Situation, Background, Assessment, Recommendation). The purpose of SBAR communication is to provide a framework for effective communication between members of the health care team and other health professionals, to provide accurate information about the patient's current condition and any recent changes that have occurred or to anticipate when changes occur and to help staff become patient advocates. [8]. The implementation of SBAR communication in the ICU Room at Panembahan Senopati Hospital Bantul in the excellent category indicated with information about the socialization of SBAR communication obtained by nurses through training education, information from superiors, friends, circulating information media, increasing nurses' knowledge to apply SBAR communication better. Several previous studies also showed that the effective communication of SBAR carried out by nurses was in a suitable category as in the [9], which examined the description of the implementation of effective SBAR communication at the Banda Aceh Hospital. Well. Likewise, research conducted by [10] found the results that nurses had carried out effective communication at the time of weighing well (40%) and very well (30%). [11] Examined the implementation of SBAR communication on nurses in the surgical and internal wards of Dr. M Djamil Padang Hospital, and the results were optimal.

Nurse Motivation

The findings in table 4.6 show that ICU nurses have good motivation in carrying out nursing care for patients. According to the researcher's assumption, work motivation needs to be owned by a nurse because it can encourage nurses to be more responsible and enthusiastic at work. Work motivation for good nurses is one of the factors that can improve the quality and service quality [12].

The results of this study support research conducted by [13], which shows that the motivation of most nurses is high in carrying out nursing care at Bhayangkara Hospital. [14] proved in their research that there were 36 nurses (53.7%) who had high motivation at the Jati Sempurna Hospital in carrying out patient safety measures.

Motivation is a strong driver that contributes significantly to the organization's success for the achievement of goals. The success of an organization in achieving its goals is if there is support for all components and has maximum efforts in its performance. Principles in providing work motivation for nurses include participatory principles, communication, acknowledgment of subordinates' contributions, and delegation of authority [15].

Based on the questionnaire results to 12 respondents, one nurse had the lowest motivation score. However, the score

can categorize as good motivation. This shows that the role of the leader has a strong influence on increasing intrinsic and extrinsic motivation such as a sense of being needed and meaningful at work, recognition of their work, being given the freedom to express opinions, understanding success and achievement at work [16]. [17], the strong motivation that all nurses have will succeed in providing the best service.

Nurse Performance

The behavior of nurses in nursing services in the ICU based on this study was performing well. Performance is success in completing targeted tasks, while the quality and quantity of a nurse in carrying out their duties is in line with the mandated responsibilities [15]. The quality of nursing services has a relationship with the performance of nurses, so the benchmark for service quality is how to evaluate the performance of nurses [18]. The method of assessing nurse performance is based on standards of nursing practice [19]. The principle of nurse performance is measured from the implementation of nursing care and serves as a measurement in carrying out nursing service practices [20]

Service behavior in the nursing field is a response or action taken to patients with their wants and needs [17]. Nursing service is an action in helping other individuals from birth to death who are sick or healthy in the form of knowledge, will, and abilities so that these individuals can carry out daily activities more optimally and independently [21].

Several previous studies that support the results of this study include research conducted by [22] regarding the Overview of Nurse Performance in the Implementation of Nursing Care in the Lontara Inpatient Installation, Dr. Wahidin Sudirohusodo Hospital, it was found that the nurse's performance at 52.2% was good. The research results by [23] describe the performance of 83 nurse respondents, the results of the nurse's performance in the inpatient room at the AN-NISA Hospital Tangerang in the excellent category, namely 44 (53.0%). Meanwhile, research by [24] nurse performance is the activity of nurses in implementing their duties properly and being responsible for achieving the main goals of the profession and organization. The study results found that most of the respondents were 56%, nurses had good performance preparation, and 44% had a poorly prepared performance.

Services in the nursing field are the spearhead of the health services of a hospital that serves patients 24 hours continuously. The provision of nursing services should carry out with accuracy, speed, accuracy, and satisfaction. Having proper behavior towards general patients and participants of national health insurance, communicating and conveying health information, meeting patient needs, and alerting nurses in inpatient care [25].

Nurses need high motivation and effective communication to support quality nursing services to improve patient safety. However, about the effect of effective communication on

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nurse service behavior, this study shows that the value of $p = 0.920$ ($p > 0.005$) is obtained in an analytical test. Thus, there is no influence between compelling communication work motivation on the behavior of nursing services for ICU nurses at Panembahan Senopati Hospital Bantul.

Effective Communication Relationship with Nurse Performance

There was no relationship between communication and nursing service behavior in this study. Comparison of scores for each component of effective communication also found that nurses with good performance had a higher average score for implementing background, implementing assessments, and implementing recommendations. Meanwhile, nurses with poor performance have a higher mean score of SBAR knowledge. However, there is no difference in the mean score of SBAR knowledge, background, assessment, and recommendation application between nurses with good performance and nurses with poor performance (all have $p\text{-value} > 0.05$). This means that nurses with good performance and nurses with poor performance have a level of knowledge of SBAR, application of background, application of assessment, and application of recommendations that can be equivalent so that the various components of effective communication do not affect their performance.

This result contradicts what was stated by [26], where effective communication in collaboration with fellow health workers is a component that can improve the quality of nurse services to patients and the safety of these patients. The American Nurses Association suggests that effective communication is a requirement for professional nursing practice, clinical and psychomotor diagnostic skills. Communication and interpersonal skills are also professional competencies in nursing practice [27]. This study is in line with the research of [28], which showed that there was no relationship between effective communication and nurse performance with a $p\text{-value} = 0.056$ ($p > 0.05$).

The Relationship between Nurse's Motivation and Nurse's Performance

Identical to the findings on effective communication, the work motivation of nurses in this study also did not affect the performance of nurses. This result also supports a per component analysis of nurses' motivation. It was found that nurses with good performance had a higher average motivation score in terms of recognition/award than nurses with poor performance. Meanwhile, nurses with poor performance have a higher average motivation score regarding responsibility, promotion, interpersonal relations, supervision, and working conditions than nurses with good performance. However, there was no difference in the mean scores for the components of recognition/award, achievement, responsibility, promotion, interpersonal relations, salary, supervision, and working conditions (all

had $p > 0.05$). This means that nurses with good performance and poor performance feel recognition/award, achievement, responsibility, promotion, interpersonal relationships, salaries, supervision, and working conditions are almost the same. Some of these motivational components do not affect their performance.

The results of this study contradict the opinion [19] that the performance of nurses is influenced by work motivation. In line with research [29], there was no relationship between work motivation and nurse performance. The statistical test results obtained $p\text{-value} = 0.076$ ($p > 0.05$). In line with research [30], finding work motivation does not affect the performance of medical record officers.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

1. Effective communication with nurses in the ICU Room at Panembahan Senopati Hospital Bantul is good.
2. Work motivation for nurses in the ICU Room at Panembahan Senopati Hospital Bantul is good.
3. The behavior of nurses in the ICU room at Panembahan Senopati Hospital Bantul is good.
4. Effective communication and work motivation of nurses do not affect the performance of nurses in the ICU Room at Panembahan Senopati Hospital, Bantul.

Suggestion

1. For Hospital Institutions
The results of this study can consider for hospital institutions in making policies to improve nurses' effective communication and work motivation to improve nursing service behavior.
2. For educational institutions
The results of this study expect to add to the literature reference, especially regarding effective communication and work motivation, and nursing service behavior.
3. For other researchers.
Other researchers expected to develop the results of this study by examining other factors that may be related to effective communication and work motivation of nurses to improve nursing service behavior.

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